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A simple methodology to collect culturable bacteria from feces of *Anopheles darlingi* (Diptera: Culicidae)

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ABSTRACT

A simple methodology based in a modified mosquito cage with a Petri dish containing culture medium was successfully used as an alternative method to the traditional digestive tract dissection protocol to collect bacteria from the feces of the mosquito *Anopheles darlingi*.

Microbiota from the gut of *Anopheles* mosquitoes interact with *Plasmodium*, the parasite that causes malaria (Manguin et al., 2013; Ngo et al., 2015; Rani et al., 2009) and it may be used to develop biotechnological tools, such as paratransgenic strategies

25 (Riehle and Jacobs-Lorena, 2005; Wang and Jacobs-Lorena, 2013). However, the lack
26 of information about the mosquito's microbiota in the Americas (Villegas and Pimenta,
27 2014) still limits this strategy in the region which depends on culturable
28 microorganisms from the intestinal microbiome as prerequisite for studies and future
29 genetic manipulations necessary for the execution of the technique (Wang and Jacobs-
30 Lorena, 2013; Wilke and Marrelli, 2015).

31 For the isolation of intestinal microorganisms from mosquitoes, the gut is usually
32 dissected by skilled personnel (Consoli and Oliveira, 1994; Djadid et al., 2011; Gusmão
33 et al., 2007) and prepared for classical microbiological techniques (Tortora et al., 2012).
34 However, it is reasonable to hypothesize that mosquito feces contain microorganisms
35 that are and/or were present in the intestine of these insects.

36 The present device for collecting cultivable intestinal microorganisms from mosquito
37 feces does not require insect dissection to collect material, reducing work and external
38 contamination issues.

39 The feces collection device is based in a modified PVC mosquito cage with 3
40 compartments, namely: 1- upper compartment for feeding; 2- middle compartment
41 (body) for maintenance of mosquitoes; 3- lower compartment for collection of feces
42 (Figure 1).

43

44 **Fig 1.** Device for collection of feces from mosquitoes. (A) Front view of the mounted
45 device. 1. Upper compartment for food supply; 2. Middle compartment to contain
46 mosquitoes; 3. Lower compartment for collection of mosquito feces. (B) Top view of
47 the disassembled device.

48 The middle compartment is a 10 x 10 cm (diameter and height) PVC tube, screened on
49 both sides with a mosquito-proof nylon net (1.5 mm mesh) and a side opening covered
50 by a perforated elastic material for mosquito manipulation. The upper side contains
51 cotton soaked with 10% sucrose for mosquito feeding covered by a PVC lid (upper
52 compartment), preventing any external microorganism contamination. A PVC lid
53 containing a removable Petri dish for feces collection is placed in the lower side (lower
54 compartment). Mosquitoes are introduced into the device through the middle
55 compartment side opening, feed in the sucrose solution placed the in the upper
56 compartment and then release their feces into the lower compartment, inaccessible to
57 the mosquitoes, that keeps the Petri dishes containing LB agar culture medium (Figure
58 2).

59

60 Fig. 2 Procedure for collecting microorganisms contained in mosquito feces (A) Top
61 view of the middle compartment of the device containing mosquitoes. (B) Top view of
62 the lower compartment of the device containing the Petri Dish with culture medium. (C)
63 Front view of Petri Dish containing bacterial colonies that grew from mosquito feces.
64 (D) Partial view of Petri Dish containing specimens of bacterial colonies that were
65 isolated from mosquito feces.

66 Mosquitoes were captured in Porto Velho, Rondonia State, Brazil using a hand-held
67 aspirator, identified using identification keys (Consoli and Oliveira, 1994).

68 The Feces collection device was cleaned using water and neutral liquid soap, rinsed
69 with distilled water and then with 70% ethanol for 10 seconds and rotated after 30
70 minutes while drying under UV light inside a microbiological safety cabinet for 1 hour.
71 The devices were packed in plastic film prior to use. The sterility of internal surface of
72 feces collection device was checked after the cleaning and UV treatment using sterile

73 cotton swabs. Samples were streaked over the surface of the LB agar petri dishes and
74 incubated aerobically at 37 °C for 24 hours. No microorganism growth was observed
75 after 24 hours.

76 Batches of five mosquitoes (N=12) were introduced in the devices and fed *ad libitum*
77 using autoclaved cotton soaked in 10% autoclaved sucrose. Three mosquito-free devices
78 were used as negative controls.

79 Petri dishes containing the mosquito feces in LB agar culture were removed from the
80 lower compartment after 24 hours and incubated at 37 °C for 24 hours (Rani et al.,
81 2009). Isolated bacterial colonies with different morphologies were harvested from the
82 petri dishes, transferred to new dishes to ensure the production of pure cultures (streak
83 plate method) and stored in 15% glycerol at -70 °C.

84 The phenol/chloroform method was used to extract genomic DNA from the bacteria,
85 (Sambrook and Russel, 2001 adapted). PCR amplifications of the bacterial ribosomal
86 DNA using the primers 16S08F (GYCCADACWCCTACGG) and 16S08R
87 (CACGAGCTGACGAC) were performed for bacteria identification. Briefly, 0.5 µM of
88 each *primer*, 0.25 mM of the dNTP MIX, 2.5 mM MgCl₂, 1X reaction buffer (DNA
89 express Taq DNA Polymerase), 2 units of Taq DNA polymerase and 50 ng of each
90 bacterial genomic DNA isolated were mixed and submitted to an initial extension of
91 94°C/7 minutes; 30 cycles of 94°C/45 seconds, the annealing temperature was 50°C/30
92 seconds, 72°C/60 seconds; followed by a final extension of 72°C/10 minutes. Genomic
93 DNA from *Escherichia coli* O42 (50 ng) was used as a positive control for the reactions
94 and, a negative control was prepared using all the reagents except a DNA template. The
95 *amplicons* were purified using the *QIAquick Gel Extraction kit* (QIAGEN), according to
96 the manufacturer's specifications.

97 Sequencing was performed using the Sanger method in an ABI 3730 DNA Sequencer
98 from Life Technologies. All samples were sequenced in duplicate. The sequences were
99 treated using the software Phred-Phrap-Consed with the Phred quality score of 30. A
100 consensus sequence was generated for each isolate's *amplicon*. The consensus
101 sequences were uploaded in the Ribosomal Database Project's (RDP) Classifier for
102 taxonomic assignment (Wang et al., 2007). Sequences with 100% confidence were
103 considered using the RDP classifier hosted on the web, calibrated with a threshold of
104 80%.

105 Five colonies from each of the 12 Petri dishes were harvested for 60 new dishes, one
106 dish for each bacterial colony to ensure colony isolation. No bacterial colonies were
107 detected in the negative controls, i.e., from collection devices without mosquitoes. To
108 date, 16 bacteria colonies were identified with 100% confidence using the RDP
109 classifier, i.e., *Acinetobacter* (6) (Moraxellaceae); *Staphylococcus* (5)
110 (Staphylococcaceae); *Enterobacter* (1), *Klebsiella* (1), *Serratia* (9) (Enterobacteriaceae)
111 (Supplementary Table 1). Isolates with less than 99% confidence were not presented
112 and will be reevaluated.

113 The isolation of bacteria from mosquito's feces for microbiological analysis has
114 received little attention. We highlight the pioneering study on the experimental
115 transmission of the yellow fever virus from fecal material present in the legs of infected
116 mosquitoes (Aragão and Costa Lima, 1929) and, recently, the study conducted by
117 Pilotte et al. (2016) using the feces of the mosquito *Anopheles stephensi* for
118 xenomonitoring of the nematode *Brugia malaya* and protozoan *Plasmodium vivax*. The
119 fecal collection methodology employed by both authors was tested for isolation of
120 culturable bacteria and neither was suitable (unpublished data). On the other hand, the

121 majority of genera retrieved using the feces collection method reported here belonged to
122 the Enterobacteriaceae family as also related from whole bodies of *Anopheles darlingi*
123 (Terenius et al., 2007) and *Enterobacter* and *Serratia* were related to anophelines from
124 the Americas (see Villegas and Pimenta, 2014 for a review). Therefore, our data
125 indicates that the feces collection methodology proposed is a suitable tool for obtaining
126 culturable bacteria from mosquitoes.

127 Conflicts of interest: None

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